

Title

Lone-parent households and the risk of child poverty in Ireland: A scoping review protocol

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Review question

The review question is: What is the landscape of research on children aged 0-17 living in or at risk of poverty in lone-parent households in Ireland?

- How are lone-parent households defined and which lone parent groups are represented?
- What does the evidence say about the needs, lived experiences and characteristics of lone-parent households?
- What methods, data and measures have been used to study this topic?

Background and rationale

Children living in or at risk of poverty in lone-parent households constitute one of the most structurally disadvantaged groups in Ireland, yet the evidence base capturing their lived experiences, needs and outcomes remains fragmented across disciplines, data sources and policy domains. A scoping review is therefore methodologically appropriate, as it enables a systematic mapping of diverse forms of evidence, including peer-reviewed studies, administrative data analyses and grey literature, without restricting inclusion to specific study designs.

Following the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) scoping review methodology and the PCC framework ensures transparency and reproducibility, while the incorporation of the Arksey and O'Malley (2005) model and subsequent refinements by Levac et al. (2010) supports an iterative, reflexive approach that is particularly important when working with complex, intersectional populations. This review will make visible how poverty is conceptualised and measured across studies, how lone parent households are defined, and where methodological or population-specific gaps persist, thereby strengthening the foundations for future empirical research.

Furthermore, the rationale for this review is grounded in contemporary Irish policy imperatives, including the cross-government Child Poverty and Well-being Programme and the Irish State's commitments to evidence-informed social policy.

Lone-parent households consistently demonstrate higher rates of at-risk-of-poverty, material deprivation and consistent poverty compared with other family types, yet policy responses often span income supports, childcare, education, housing and employment systems, each with its own evidence base. By synthesising this dispersed research and generating evidence maps across domains, outcomes and population subgroups, the review will provide a coherent, policy-relevant overview of what is known, and crucially, what remains unknown, about child poverty in lone-parent households in Ireland. The planned consultation with policy stakeholders further strengthens the relevance and utility of the findings, ensuring that the review contributes meaningfully to future policy design, targeted interventions and the identification of priority measurement and research gaps.

Inclusion criteria (PCC)

Participants

Children aged 0–17 years living in lone-parent households resident in Ireland. Mixed household studies are eligible if lone parent subgroups are analysable. Lone-parent status used only as a statistical control is *not* eligible unless results relate directly to lone-parent households.

Concept

Living conditions and risk of poverty according to national definitions.

Context

Ireland (national), including island-of-Ireland and EU comparisons where Ireland data are separable.

Information sources

Peer-reviewed studies (any design), reviews, government/agency reports, datasets/data notes and preprints (prefer peer-reviewed if both exist), advocacy literature are included. Conference abstracts, theses, blog posts, opinion pieces, non-documentary web content unless directly reporting methods/data, duplicates of peer-reviewed versions found during the grey literature search are not in scope.

The team will restrict inclusion to sources from 1 January 2005 onwards to reflect significant changes in Irish and EU social policy and data infrastructure (e.g., EU-SILC availability and post-2004 policy context). English-language sources are included for feasibility and because the core Irish governmental and advocacy evidence base is published in English; language limitations will be acknowledged as a potential source of bias.

Search strategy

The search follows the JBI three-step process: (1) an initial limited search (e.g. Scopus) to test and analyse text words in titles/abstracts and index terms (2) Consultation with expert knowledge user group; (2) a refined, comprehensive search across all selected databases and grey sources; and (3) supplementary searching (citation chasing, handsearching targeted organisational sites).

Full database strategies (fields, operators, limits), interfaces/platforms and dates run will be archived and provided (PRISMA-S); deduplication will be performed in EndNote 21.5 using staged field-matching passes plus manual verification, with counts and method logged.

Bibliographic databases will include:

- Scopus
- Web of Science
- ProQuest.

Example (Scopus): TITLE-ABS-KEY ((Ireland OR Irish) AND ("lone parent*" OR "single parent*" OR "solo parent*" OR "single mother*" OR "single father*" OR "lone mother*" OR "lone father*" OR "one-parent" OR "single-parent" OR "lone caregiver*" OR "single caregiver*")) AND PUBYEAR > 2004

Grey literature searches will follow a structured pathway and be fully logged (platform, query, filters, access date/time), with unstable web content preserved via archived links where feasible. Grey literature search strings will be adapted to each platform (phrase searching, site/domain limits, filetype operators). The team will document all queries, interfaces, dates run, and applied limits; for dynamic web content the team will record access dates and store downloaded files with stable links or web archive captures where feasible. Grey literature will include targeted searches across:

- Central Statistics Office (Ireland) - including EU-SILC publications, releases and data notes.
- Government and agency portals on gov.ie (e.g., Department of Social Protection; Department of Children, Disability and Equality; Child Poverty & Well-being Programme Office; Department of the Taoiseach).
- Economic and Social Research Institute (ESRI) - reports, research notes and working papers.
- Advocacy organisations with a research remit on child poverty and lone-parent households (Barnardos; One Family; Society of St Vincent de Paul; Children's Rights Alliance; Focus Ireland).

Grey literature search quality assurance (sample verification): A single researcher will run the grey/advocacy searches. To ensure transparency and reproducibility while managing volume, a second reviewer will sample-check the grey literature searches only as follows: (i) for each organisation/site, a 10–20% sample of the search records (or a minimum of 20 items, whichever is larger) will be independently re-queried and screened against the eligibility criteria; (ii) any discrepancy rate >10% in included/excluded items or missed key documents will trigger targeted follow-up (expanded sampling or re-run of queries for that source); (iii) all checks, discrepancies and actions will be logged in the PRISMA-S search log and reported in the PRISMA flow. This sampling approach applies only to grey/advocacy sources; bibliographic database searches and screening will continue to follow the dual-reviewer process already specified.

Data management

The team will use EndNote 21.5 and Microsoft Excel to manage the data during the collection, title and abstract screening, full text screening, and data extraction phases of the review. The team will use Microsoft Excel and MAXQDA Pro 26 to manage the quantitative and qualitative data.

Selection process

Removal of duplicates will be performed using the reference management software, EndNote. Two reviewers will screen titles/abstracts independently using Excel, followed by dual full-text screening; a third reviewer will resolve disagreements. A PRISMA 2020 flow chart adapted for scoping reviews will document the process. Deduplication will use staged field-matching passes (e.g., Author+Year+Title; Title+Year+Pages/DOI) with manual verification; counts will be recorded in the PRISMA flow. In addition, for grey/advocacy sources only, a second reviewer will perform the sample-check described in the Search Strategy (10–20% or ≥ 20 items per source); discrepancies $>10\%$ will trigger follow-up checks or re-runs. All actions will be recorded in the PRISMA-S log.

Data extraction

The team will chart the following variables in MAXQDA Pro (document variables) for every included source: bibliographic metadata (authors, year, title, source type/publication status); study characteristics (design; longitudinal indicator; dataset/evidence source, e.g., EU-SILC, GUI, administrative; data linkage; sample size); population descriptors (operational definition of lone-parent household; child age bands 0–5/6–12/13–17; household composition/custody where reported; subgroup flags: disability, migrant/refugee, Traveller/Roma, LGBTQ+, rural/urban); context (geographic scope; whether Ireland-specific estimates are separable; study period); poverty measures (At-Risk-Of-Poverty, child-specific/material deprivation, consistent/persistent poverty, financial strain; recording operational definitions and instruments); policy/needs domains (income adequacy & social transfers; childcare; housing/homelessness; education; employment & in-work supports; family support/social protection; cultural norms & stigma); outcomes (child-, caregiver-, household-, and system-level indicators and measurement tools); lived-experience elements (access barriers/enablers; stigma/discrimination; service interactions with e.g. Irish Government Department of Social Protection, local authority housing); intervention/policy details and comparators where applicable; key findings and direction of effects; explicit evidence gaps and study limitations; ethics statements; and participation/co-creation level. For multi-country studies, the team will extract Ireland-specific results separately wherever possible. Items are harmonised with the review's codebook and will be confirmed during pilot charting for completeness and consistency.

Data synthesis and presentation of results

The team will present descriptive evidence maps stratified by year, method, data source, policy domain (income supports; childcare; housing/homelessness; education; employment), outcome domain, and population subgroup (including equity variables). Gap matrices (domain \times subgroup \times outcome) will highlight empty or thin cells. The narrative/thematic synthesis will summarise mechanisms and policy levers and explain heterogeneity across contexts and measurement choices. No formal risk-of-bias appraisal will be undertaken (consistent with scoping review aims), though study limitations will be noted.

Consultation

Three consultation touchpoints will be held with a policy and advocacy knowledge user group: (1) Prior to search and selection to confirm review scope and search strategy; (2) mid-review to validate coverage and emerging gaps; and (3) pre-publication to refine interpretations and policy implications.

Insights from the policy-maker and NGO (knowledge users) steering group will be incorporated during synthesis to validate emerging themes, clarify contextual interpretations, and ensure policy relevance. Their review of preliminary findings will also support the confirmation of evidence gaps and highlight priority areas requiring further investigation.

Registration and reporting

Scoping reviews are not eligible for PROSPERO. The protocol will be registered on OSF Registries (template: Open-ended Registration), which creates a time-stamped, read-only snapshot and mints a DataCite DOI. Any amendments to the protocol will be documented via OSF “Updates” with brief rationale and date-stamp.

In addition, we will archive a public copy on Zenodo (EU Open Research Repository community) for discoverability and versioning; the OSF registration DOI and the Zenodo DOI(s) will be cross-linked. Reporting will follow PRISMA-ScR, with search methods reported to PRISMA-S standards.

Ethics and reflexivity

There are no human participants; ethics approval not required. A reflexivity memo will be maintained in MAXQDA Pro 26 to document decisions, assumptions and knowledge user influence.

Responsible use of AI:

Compliance with Government of Ireland ‘Guidelines on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in the Public Service’. Artificial Intelligence will not be used for screening, full text review or the reporting of findings. MAXQDA Pro in-built AI Assist research tool may support thematic analysis.

Source of funding

The review is funded by the Department of Children, Disability and Equality (DCDE), Government of Ireland.

Roles and responsibilities

The funder has no role in developing the protocol. The draft journal articles will be submitted as deliverables to the funders and will be peer reviewed by an external expert during the project. PI: Methodological integrity and arbitration. Researcher: Search design/execution, EndNote management, PRISMA-S log, dual screening and coding using MAXQDA Pro software. Knowledge user steering group: Engagement and validation.

Anticipated or actual start date:

2026-04-01

Anticipated completion date:

2026-09-30

Current status:

Ongoing

Methodological references

Arksey, H., & O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: Towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 8(1), 19–32.

Levac, D., Colquhoun, H., & O'Brien, K. K. (2010). Scoping studies: Advancing the methodology. *Implementation Science*, 5, 69.

Department of Public Expenditure, Infrastructure, Public Service Reform and Digitalisation. (2025). *Guidelines for the responsible use of artificial intelligence in the public service*. Government of Ireland.

Peters, M. D. J., Godfrey, C., McInerney, P., Munn, Z., Tricco, A. C., & Khalil, H. (2020). Scoping reviews. In E. Aromataris et al. (Eds.), *JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis* (2024). JBI. <https://synthesismanual.jbi.global> <https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-24-09>

Rethlefsen, M. L., Kirtley, S., Waffenschmidt, S., et al. (2021). PRISMA-S: An extension to the PRISMA statement for reporting literature searches in systematic reviews. *Systematic Reviews*, 10, 39.

Tricco, A. C., Lillie, E., Zarin, W., O'Brien, K. K., Colquhoun, H., Levac, D., et al. (2018). PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and explanation. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 169(7), 467–473.

Appendix 1: Template PRISMA-S Search Reporting Tables¹

Table A1. Bibliographic database – test search example

Database	Platform / interface	Coverage (years / collections)	Full search strategy (fielded query)	Limits / filters applied	Date run	Records retrieved (n)	Notes / permalink
Scopus	Advanced search Elsevier Scopus	All years available on Scopus at the date of search	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((Ireland OR Irish) AND ("lone parent*" OR "single parent*" OR "solo parent*" OR "single mother*" OR "single father*" OR "lone mother*" OR "lone father*" OR "one-parent" OR "single-parent" OR "lone caregiver*" OR "single caregiver*")) AND PUBYEAR > 2004	Publication year ≥ 2005	2026-03-13	156	Canonical permalink: OSF registration DOI [insert OSF DOI] (protocol; full strategies & search log). Public archive: Zenodo concept DOI [insert concept DOI] (versioned public copy). Saved search: “[Lone Parents]” ([RP]); Alert/RSS: [freq]. Re-run via Advanced search → Advanced query using the string archived on OSF.

¹ Full tables will appear in appendices upon final search.

Table A2. Grey literature and organisational sources – test search example

Organisation / website	Search location or section	Search terms / approach	Filters applied	Date accessed (YYYY-MM-DD)	Records screened (n)	Included (n)	Notes / archive link
ESRI	ESRI/Google	site:https://www.esri.ie/ "lone parent" OR "single parent" OR "solo parent" OR "single mother" OR "single father" OR "lone mother" OR "lone father" OR "one-parent" OR "single-parent" OR "single caregiver" OR "lone caregiver" filetype:pdf	2005-2026	01/04/2026	166	36	Query & access fully logged in OSF search log (DOI: [insert OSF DOI]); archived capture (e.g., Wayback): [insert archived link].

Table A3. Deduplication summary (example – test only)

Step	Tool & version	Match fields used	Records removed (n)	Records remaining (n)	Notes
1	EndNote 21.5	Author+Year+Title	74	292	Records merged and de-duplicated automatically in EndNote 21.5 (Clarivate) using "Find Duplicates" (default settings) following test searches (Scopus + ProQuest + Web of Science) performed on 2026-03-13.